

THE ROLE OF TEACHERS IN 21ST CENTURY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7188858>

Annotation

Technology nowadays has entered into every walk of life. In this era of technology, the digital revolution has transformed almost everything from our work at our organizations to our daily routine. This revolution has profoundly entered in the education sector and that is also at all levels i.e. school level, College level and university level. Teachers of 21st century have to create students of 21st century with soft skills. The 21st century teachers need teaching skills content mastery as well as integrating teaching with technology.

Keyword: characteristics of 21st century teacher, digital age, technology, the process of learning, education system.

In digital world education has become new challenge for teachers that need to pay attention for. If learning system still applies a conventional system, it may be behind the modern education system. In digital world, the process of learning and teaching is not only focused in the classroom, but also by using digital media, online and teleconference. However, the students must be controlled by the teachers, so they can choose positive aspects of technological advance. And the teachers as the main role should keep on watch and have to smarter than the students in technological issues.

Great students are the result of great teachers. The rise of communication technology and other scientific advances the role of the teacher is also questioned by some parts of society. Some even suggest that teaching profession will be redundant in the future – students can simply learn everything they need to know from YouTube or something of that effect. Thus, the teaching profession is facing criticism from many sides. Luckily, many people do realize that the students' achievement is influence by many factors. The existence of teachers among students are more important, because the teacher is the main learning resource for the students. As a source of learning, teachers must prepare with all required skills to transfer knowledge to students. Of course in this way the ability of teacher will make the students with very easy to accept knowledge.

How to qualify teachers professionally in the age of the digital age. In the Educational Leadership writes that to be a professional, a teacher is required to have five characteristics:

1. The teacher is committed to the students and the learning process. This means that the teacher's highest commitment is to interest of the students.
2. Master and utilize classical and modern learning media
3. Teachers deeply master the material / subject taught and teach it to students. For teachers, these are two things cannot be separated.
4. Teachers are responsible for monitoring student learning outcomes through various evaluation techniques, ranging from observations in student behavior to learning outcomes.
5. The teacher is able to think systematically about what he does, learn from his experience. That is, there should always be time for teachers to make reflections and corrections to what has done. To be able to learn from experience, he must know what is right and wrong, and good and bad impact on student learning process.
6. The teacher has to create an invitational environment for learning to occur. "I never teach my pupils, I only attempt to provide the conditions in which they can learn" Albert Einstein.

A teacher that is considered as a professional in the digital era is not having the ability in education and mastering educational technology, but also ability or have intrapersonal, intellectual, emotional and spiritual intelligence. Today we must have competent teachers who have a new set of resources and techniques. Technological aids is an integral part in effective learning.

I conclude by saying of Dr. Karan Singh, 'We should develop our youth, who is in higher secondary and colleges in such a way so there every activity should be for the progress of the country.'

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